

Field-programmable gate array-based field-oriented control for permanent magnet synchronous motor drive

Nam Duong Le^{1,2}, Le Quang Linh¹, Nguyen Tien Huy Cong¹, Phuong Vu¹, Tung Lam Nguyen¹

¹School of Electrical Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Hanoi, Vietnam

²Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Quy Nhon University, Binh Dinh, Vietnam

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 11, 2022

Revised Jun 28, 2022

Accepted Aug 11, 2022

Keywords:

Field programmable gate array

High power density

PMSM drives

Three phase inverters

ABSTRACT

Permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) is a special type of synchronous electric motor that has many applications such as in the manufacturing industry of robots, self-propelled mechanisms, in the medical field. In this paper, the permanent magnet synchronous motor control structure according to the field-oriented control (FOC) algorithm will be implemented on the field-programmable gate array (FPGA) card. Function blocks in FOC algorithm for example PI controller, space vector pulse width modulation (SVPWM) algorithm will be integrated into individual integrated circuit (ICs) then will be connected to form an IC with the function of implementing FOC algorithm. Furthermore, this algorithm will be used for powertrains using gallium nitride (GaN). GaN technology provides switching frequencies up to 100 kHz instead of the upper 2 to 20 kHz like insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) transistors. With GaN technology, it is possible to reduce switching losses as well as increase the efficiency of the power converter. The performance results will be verified through the typhoon hardware in the loop (HIL) device.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Phuong Vu

School of Electrical Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology

No. 1, Dai Co Viet Road, Hai Ba Trung, Hanoi, Vietnam

Email: phuong.vuhoang@hust.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

Permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) has outstanding advantages: very high efficiency up to 97.5%, the rotor speed is equal to stator magnetic field speed, so it is very stable and accurate in all adjustment areas speed. Many algorithms have been developed to improve control quality [1]. Besides, materials science is developing strongly, including research direction on high power density in the field of power electronics. Not only meet the power but also ensure the size in many applications example electric vehicles, airplanes [2]. Semiconductor technology using gallium nitride (GaN) material that allows switching with frequencies from 50 Hz to 200 Hz instead of 2 to 20 kHz in insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) transistors [3]. Besides, GaN technology also allows operation at high temperatures and reduces switching losses. The efficiency of GaN technology is practically proven in DC/DC converters [4] or 3-phase voltage source inverters (VSI) [5]. However, to be compatible with large switching frequencies, the computing power of the microcontroller must be compatible. For example, in motor control if the switching frequency is 100 kHz, the current loop control must also be sampled at the corresponding 100 kHz, so the calculating time should be less than 10 μ s. With a high sampling frequency, the microcontroller's resources will be limited since with a microcontroller we cannot perform many functions, and the control loops are limited [6]. Field-programmable gate array (FPGA) technology [7] provides multithreading capabilities, allowing high-frequency sampling [8] would be the appropriate choice. Furthermore, FPGA manufacturers also provide a system-on-chip (SoC)

environment useful for designers to synthesize, collect, and verify results [9]–[17], so FPGA technology is currently being widely used in transmission and power electronics.

In this paper, the field-oriented control (FOC) algorithm will be implemented manually using the very high speed integrated circuit (VHSIC) hardware description language (VHDL) language on the Xilinx Zybo Zynq 7010 FPGA platform. Manual implementation of the algorithm helps us to understand the architecture of the FPGA and to be able to reuse the function block capabilities in other studies. They will be described in the next section. Figure 1 depicts the structure of the FOC algorithm that will be implemented in this work.

Figure 1. Block diagram of field-oriented control algorithm for permanent magnet synchronous motors drive

2. IMPLEMENTING FOC ALGORITHM ON FPGA

This section will present in detail the FOC algorithm to control the PMSM motor. The component blocks in Figure 1 correspond to a library packaged (IP) or an integrated circuit (IC). All these IP can be reused in other projects. We refer to [15]–[25] paper for algorithm implementation.

2.1. FOC algorithm and modeling the permanent magnet synchronous motors

The three-phase AC motor has a complex structure, and it has caused considerable difficulty in the mathematical description of the isolation characteristics that can be used to independently control the two flux-generating current components (excitation circuit current) and torque generating a current (armature circuit current). The field-oriented control provides a tool that allows separating the flux-generating current (I_{sd}) and torque-generating current (I_{sq}) components from the 3-phase alternating current flowing in the stator windings of the motor (I_{sa}, I_{sb}, I_{sc}). The drive system controlled by the FOC method is a system that operates on the principle of isolating the above current components using a stator current regulating loop.

The (1), (2), (3), (4) are the equations describing the dynamics of the pmsm motor on the rotation coordinate system dq . Through these equations, we can calculate the parameters for the current controller and the speed controller.

$$u_{sd} = L_{sd} \frac{di_{sd}}{dt} + R_s i_{sd} - \omega_e L_{sq} i_{sq} \quad (1)$$

$$u_{sq} = L_{sq} \frac{di_{sq}}{dt} + R_s i_{sq} + \omega_e L_{sd} i_{sd} + \omega_e \psi_f \quad (2)$$

$$M_{dc} = \frac{3}{2} p_p [\psi_f i_{sq} + (L_{sd} - L_{sq}) i_{sd} i_{sq}] = M_{db} + M_a \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\omega_e(t)}{dt} = \frac{z_p}{J_m} (M_{dc} - \frac{B_v}{z_p} \omega_e(t) - T_l) \quad (4)$$

Assume the parameters of the induction motor are stator resistance R_s , magnetic flux ψ_f number of pairs pole p_p , axial and transverse inductance L_{sd}, L_{sq} , synchronous speed, electric speed ω_e .

2.2. Measurement of feedback current by XADC in FPGA

XADC is an analog-to-digital converters (ADC) module integrated into the Xilinx FPGA series. XADC includes 2 channels of 12bit ADC, a built-in sensor, and 1 megasamples per second (MSPS) sampling rate. In this topic, we will use XADC to measure the stator current of the motor, so we will use analog input measurement pins to perform the measurement. XADC is a 2-channel ADC, measuring the voltage difference between 2 pins P and N to convert data. It has 2 operating modes, unipolar measurement mode, and bipolar measurement mode.

In this article, we will use the unipolar mode of ADC. In unipolar mode, XADC has a measuring range from 0 to 1V. Converts to the corresponding value from 000h to FFFh without accents. If the potential difference between the two terminals P and N is less than 0V, the conversion value is 000h, or greater than 1V, the conversion value is FFFh. Since the ADC is 12 bit wide, 1 least significant bit (LSB) will correspond to $1/4095 \approx 0.244e-3 V = 0.244 \mu V$. To measure the current by XADC, we convert the stator phase current into a voltage according to the (5).

$$U(V) = 0.01 \cdot I(A) + 0.5 \tag{5}$$

Where I is the instantaneous value at the time of measurement (A), U is the voltage value applied to the XADC. From (5) we see the input voltage to XADC will be in the range of 0 to 1V. Since 1 LSB of XADC corresponds to 0.244uV, we will calculate the measurement limit in this case.

2.3. Measurement the feedback speed of PMSM

To measure the motor speed, we use the Incremental encoder to output pulses on two channels a and b. The pulses on 2 channels will be transmitted to the digital input pin of the FPGA, where we will perform computational programming to calculate the motor speed. If you do it the same way, surely the reading speed value will be wrong. The closer the encoder is to the motor, the more noise, the larger the motor power, the more noise. Therefore, it is necessary to prevent interference by both hardware and software.

In this paper, I read the encode pulse value at 4 different times t1, t2, t3, t4 through which we can know whether the motor is rotating forward or backward in Figure 2. To calculate motor speed, we count the encodercount in a constant time. At this time, the encodercount variable will be equivalent to the rotation angle of the motor, dividing this value with the predetermined time will get the speed of the motor. In this application, we will perform rate sampling with a frequency of 2000 Hz. Since the clock frequency is 1 MHz, we will use a counter to count every time the counter counts up to the value 500, we multiply the encodercount variable by a constant to get the motor speed.

Assume that when the variable counter is overflow, encodercount's value is x, the number of pole pairs is z_p , encoder has n pulses per revolution (PPR), the electrical rotor speed is calculated (6). Set the values of z_p , n depending on the parameter of motor and encoder.

$$\omega_e = x \cdot \frac{2000 \cdot z_p}{4 \cdot n} \cdot 2\pi(rad/s) \tag{6}$$

Figure 2. The logic stage of incremental encoder channels

2.4. Coordinate system conversion

According to Figure 1, the speed controller creates input for q -axis current controller and the input of the d -axis controller is zero by default. These inputs will be compared with the responses from the current sensor which was converted through clark transformation and park transformation (known as alpha-beta transformation and dq transformation respectively). The output of these controllers, which is in dq frame will be transformed to $\alpha\beta$ frame through dq to $\alpha\beta$ transformation and then feed the SVM module. The following Table 1 show details about dq and ab transformation.

To deploy the dq and ab transformation module in the FPGA card the (7) to (12) equations is introduced. The trigonometric functions $\sin(\theta)$ and $\cos(\theta)$ will be determined by using the look-up-table method. All this data will be moved to transformation module, from there can significantly reduce processing time because retrieving a value from memory is often faster than carrying out a computation.

Table 1. Formula for frame transformation

Clarke transform	Park transforms	Invert park transform
$\begin{cases} I_{sa} = I_{sa} \cdot \frac{2}{3} - I_{sb} \cdot \frac{1}{3} - I_{sc} \cdot \frac{1}{3} & (7) \\ I_{sb} = I_{sb} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} - I_{sc} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & (8) \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} I_{sd} = I_{sa} \cdot \cos(\theta) + I_{sb} \cdot \sin(\theta) & (9) \\ I_{sq} = I_{sb} \cdot \cos(\theta) - I_{sa} \cdot \sin(\theta) & (10) \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} U_{sa} = U_{sd} \cdot \cos(\theta) - U_{sq} \cdot \sin(\theta) & (11) \\ U_{sa} = U_{sd} \cdot \sin(\theta) + U_{sq} \cdot \cos(\theta) & (12) \end{cases}$

2.5. Discrete PI controller

PI controller is very popular in the industry. This kind of controller is supposed the most effective controller for motor control. In this paper, PI controller will be used for both speed and current controller. The speed controller generates the stator current reference I_{sq}^* (I_{sd}^* is zero by default), the outputs of current controllers are stator voltage U_{sd} and U_{sq} , which become the input of the digital SVPWM module. The PI controller is described in a differential as in (13).

$$u(t) = K_p \cdot e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt \quad (13)$$

Where K_p is the proportional gain, K_i is the integral time constant, $e(t)$ is the error (different between reference and feedback) and $u(t)$ is the control signal of the controller. The (13) illustrates a continuous PI controller so to implement it on FPGA platform, a discrete one is needed. With the sample period T , the (13) also can become a difference equation by discretization as:

$$u(k) = I(k-1) + K_p e(k) + \frac{K_i}{T_s} \cdot e(k) \quad (14)$$

The (14) illustrate a digital PI, it can be used for any digital controller, so is FPGA. Nevertheless, because of discretization with sampling time T so the quality of control will deplete. To reduce this effect, the smaller the sampling time is, the more effect is eliminated, l so the anti-windup is added to reduce the overshooting problem.

- Saturation flag to control the anti-windup component.
- when saturation = '1', the controller is in saturation condition, the integral component is removed to prevent control signal from overshoot.
- When saturation = '0', the controller is not in saturation condition and work as a normal PI controller.

2.7. Space vector PWM technique

Space vector modulation (SVM) is a technique used for pulse width modulation (PWM); it is commonly applied for voltage source inverter (VSI). The biggest advantage of this technique is that it can utilize up to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}$ time of DC side voltage ($\approx 0.577 U_{dc}$) compared to only $0.5 U_{dc}$ of the Sin PWM technique. In this research, it will be programmed to generate the gate pulse at frequency 100 kHz for 2-level VSI using GaN devices. The SVM algorithm divides the space vector on the stationary $\alpha\beta$ frame into 6 sectors by the basic vectors V_1 to V_6 shown in Figure 3, moreover, there are also two zero-vectors V_0 and V_7 .

Any voltage-vector in the $\alpha\beta$ frame belongs to one of these six sectors and can be synthesized from two adjacent basic vectors and two zero vectors. For example, with vector u in Figure 3, it is the result of the synthesis from u_1 , u_2 , and zero-vector according to the relation: $u = d_1 u_1 + d_2 u_2 + d_0 V_{0/7}$ (15). Where d_0 , d_1 , d_2 is the duty-ratio of each vector, which is determined by the (16), (17).

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{3}{2 \cdot U_{dc}} \cdot M_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_\alpha \\ u_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$d_o = 1 - d_1 - d_2 \tag{17}$$

Where M_k is a 2x2 matrix that depends on the sector as shown in Table 2. The duty ratio after being determined will be used to calculate d_a, d_b, d_c using the formula in Table 3, which is the duty cycle of the high side switch in the voltage source inverter. When finishing the calculation, they will be compared with triangle carrier waveform at frequency 100 kHz to generate the gate pulse to high-side switch, low-side switch gate pulse is the inverse of the high-side switch gate pulse. From the theory and equations presented above, the SVPWM technique is programmed on the FPGA platform, Figure 4 shows the block diagram of its implementation in this research. Each block is equivalent to an register-transfer level (RTL) module in FPGA design and connected by the interconnect wires.

Figure 3. Basic vector and 6 sectors

Figure 4. Block diagram of SVPWM technique in FPGA xilinx

Table 2. Value of matrix M_k

Sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
M_k	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 1 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ -1 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ -1 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & -1 \\ 1 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3} \end{bmatrix}$

Table 3. Duty cycle for each sector

Sector	1	2	3	4	5	6
d_a	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_2$	$d_0/2$	$d_0/2$	$d_0/2 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$
d_b	$d_0/2 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_2$	$d_0/2$	$d_0/2$
d_c	$d_0/2$	$d_0/2$	$d_0/2 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_1 + d_2$	$d_0/2 + d_2$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows some test results with hardware in the loop (HIL) storm to show the validity of the study. FPGA and HIL storm connection diagram is shown in Figure 5, experimental model is given in Figure 6 and parameters are given in Table 4 and Table 5. Figure 6 presents the structural diagram of HIL experimental system.

Table 4. Parameters of pmsm

R_s	L_{sd}	L_{sq}	R_r	J	Pole pairs	Flux linkage
0.5 Ω	0.0022 H	0.0022 H	0.97 Ω	3.24e-3 Kg.m/s ²	4	0.1861 Wb

Table 5. Parameters of VSI circuit and controllers

VSI circuit		Controller			
Parameters	Value	Controller	K_p	K_i	Limit
U_{dc} :	600 V	Speed controller	0.26	2.01	± 22
f_{sw} :	100 kHz	Current controller	8.60	227.27	± 18

Figure 5. Connecting FPGA and Typhoon HIL

Figure 6. The experimental setup

3.1. Resource usage and processing time

Where we see that the calculation speed of the FPGA is quite fast $0.22 \mu s$ while the sampling period is $10 \mu s$ as shown in Figure 7 from there we can use the calculation results for other purposes instead of waiting for the next period. resources used the account for $1/3 \rightarrow 1/2$ of the total resources of the FPGA shown in Table 6. Thus, designer can choose the appropriate allocation and the corresponding scheduling which fit the best his application.

Table 6. Device utilization in FPGA board

Resource	Used	Available	Utilization (%)
Look Up Table (LUT)	6232	17600	35.41
Flip Flop (FF)	1751	35200	4.97
BRAM	1	60	47.6
DSP	24	80	30.00
IO	18	100	18.00

Figure 7. Processing time in FPGA

3.2. Result when launching with typhoon HIL devices

This section will show the three-phase stator current response of pmsm motor when load is Nm, there by showing the efficiency of FOC algorithm when implemented on fpga card. The sinusoidal stator current response evaluation of FOC control structures at speed of 280 rad/s are expressed through Figure 8(a), Figure 9(a) and Figure 8(b), Figure 9(b) with speed of 30 rad/s when variable load. Figure 10 shows the appropriate speed and torque response to the requirements. The amplitude, frequency of the current and the motor speed are in full agreement with the theory.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Stator current of 1st scenario when speed command is: (a) 280 rad/s and (b) 30 rad/s scenario 2: operating with constant load -15Nm

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. Stator current of 2nd scenario when speed command is: (a) 280 rad/s and (b) 30 rad/s

Figure 10. Torque and speed response

4. CONCLUSION

The implementation of a vector control algorithm using FPGA for permanent magnet synchronous motor drive was successfully developed by manual coding method in this contribution. PMSM motor can operate in a wide speed range with a single parameter of PI controller. The results in the paper show the effectiveness of FPGA cards in power electronics applications. Shows that it is possible to integrate an algorithm into a dedicated IC and we can reuse this integrated IC in many different cases. In some cases, FPGA cards can completely replace current microcontrollers to increase the system's performance in computing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is funded by the ministry of education and training (Vietnam) under project number CT2020.02.BKA-06.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. S. Razaq and J. -W. Jung, "A comprehensive review of state-of-the-art parameter estimation techniques for permanent magnet synchronous motors in wide speed range," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 16, no. 7, pp. 4747–4758, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TII.2019.2944413.
- [2] R. Lai *et al.*, "A high-power-density converter," *IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 4–12, 2010, doi: 10.1109/MIE.2010.938722.
- [3] K. Shirabe *et al.*, "Efficiency comparison between si-IGBT-based drive and GaN-based drive," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 566–572, 2014, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2013.2290812.
- [4] F. Canales, P. Barbosa, C. Aguilar, and F. C. Lee, "A high-power-density DC/DC converter for high-power distributed power systems," in *IEEE 34th Annual Conference on Power Electronics Specialist, 2003. PESC '03.*, 2003, vol. 1, pp. 11–18, doi: 10.1109/PESC.2003.1218267.
- [5] H. Li *et al.*, "Design of a 10 kW GaN-based high power density three-phase inverter," in *2016 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, 2016, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/ECCE.2016.7855019.
- [6] A. O. Rait and P. Bhosale, "FPGA implementation of space vector PWM for speed control of 3-phase induction motor," in *2011 International Conference on Recent Advancements in Electrical, Electronics and Control Engineering*, 2011, pp. 221–225, doi: 10.1109/ICONRAEECE.2011.6129782.
- [7] J. J. R. -Andina, M. J. Moure, and M. D. Valdes, "Features, design tools, and application domains of FPGAs," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 1810–1823, 2007, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2007.898279.
- [8] R. Joost and R. Salomon, "Advantages of FPGA-based multiprocessor systems in industrial applications," in *31st Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, 2005. IECON 2005.*, 2005, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2005.1568946.
- [9] J. L. Bastos, H. P. Figueroa, and A. Monti, "FPGA implementation of neural network-based controllers for power electronics applications," in *Twenty-First Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition, 2006. APEC '06.*, 2006, doi: 10.1109/APEC.2006.1620729.
- [10] E. T. Mekonnen, J. Katcha, and M. Parker, "An FPGA-based digital control development method for power electronics," in *IECON 2012 - 38th Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, 2012, pp. 222–226, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2012.6388804.

- [11] P. Le-Huy, S. Guerette, L. A. Dessaint, and H. Le-Huy, "Real-Time simulation of power electronics in power systems using an FPGA," in *2006 Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 2006, pp. 873–877, doi: 10.1109/CCECE.2006.277356.
- [12] E. Monmasson, L. Idkhajine, I. Bahri, M. -W. -Naouar, and L. Charaabi, "Design methodology and FPGA-based controllers for power electronics and drive applications," in *2010 5th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications*, 2010, pp. 2328–2338, doi: 10.1109/ICIEA.2010.5515585.
- [13] M. V. Chung, D. T. Anh, and P. Vu, "A finite set-model predictive control based on FPGA platform for eleven-level cascaded H-Bridge inverter fed induction motor drive," *International Journal of Power Electronics and Drive Systems (IJPEDS)*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 845–857, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijpeds.v12.i2.pp845-857.
- [14] W. Zhao, B. H. Kim, A. C. Larson, and R. M. Voyles, "FPGA implementation of closed-loop control system for small-scale robot," in *ICAR '05. Proceedings., 12th International Conference on Advanced Robotics, 2005.*, 2005, pp. 70–77, doi: 10.1109/ICAR.2005.1507393.
- [15] T. D. Do, N. D. Le, V. H. Phuong, and N. T. Lam, "Implementation of FOC algorithm using FPGA for GaN-based three phase induction motor drive," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 636–645, 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i2.3569.
- [16] Y. -S. Kung, C. -S. Chen, K. -I. Wong, and M. -H. Tsai, "Development of a FPGA-based Control IC for PMSM Drive with Adaptive Fuzzy Control," *31st Annual Conference of IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, 2005. IECON 2005.*, 2005, doi: 10.1109/IECON.2005.1569134.
- [17] Q. B. Dang, N. D. Ngoc, V. H. Phuong, and M. C. Ta, "Implementation of frequency-approach-based energy management for EVs using typhoon HIL402," in *2019 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, 2019, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/VPPC46532.2019.8952271.
- [18] V. T. Ha, V. H. Phuong, N. T. Lam, and N. P. Quang, "A dead-beat current controller based wind turbine emulator," in *2017 International Conference on System Science and Engineering (ICSSE)*, 2017, pp. 169–174, doi: 10.1109/ICSSE.2017.8030859.
- [19] L. N. Duong, V. H. Phuong, N. V. Lien, and T. T. Minh, "A modified deadbeat current controller for field oriented induction motor drivers," in *2021 International Conference on System Science and Engineering (ICSSE)*, 2021, pp. 241–245, doi: 10.1109/ICSSE52999.2021.9538495.
- [20] A. M. Eltamaly, "FPGA based speed control of three-phase induction motor using stator voltage regulator," *Mansoura Engineering Journal*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 93–100, 2020. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236645340_FPGA_Based_Speed_Control_of_Three-Phase_Induction_Motor_Using_Stator_Voltage_Regulator
- [21] M. Sulaiman, F. A. Patakor, and Z. Ibrahim, "DSP based implementation of field oriented control of three-phase induction motor drives," *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 02, no. 09, pp. 179–186, 2013, doi: 10.15623/ijret.2013.0209027.
- [22] J. Bocker and S. Mathapati, "State of the art of induction motor control," in *2007 IEEE International Electric Machines & Drives Conference*, 2007, pp. 1459–1464, doi: 10.1109/IEMDC.2007.383643.
- [23] V. Vlatkovic and D. Borojevic, "Digital-signal-processor-based control of three-phase space vector modulated converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 326–332, 1994, doi: 10.1109/41.293903.
- [24] M. Maruffuzzaman, M. B. I. Reaz, and M. A. M. Ali, "FPGA implementation of an intelligent current dq PI controller for FOC PMSM drive," in *2010 International Conference on Computer Applications and Industrial Electronics*, 2010, pp. 602–605, doi: 10.1109/ICCAIE.2010.5735005.
- [25] M. A. Bevilaqua, A. Nied, and J. de Oliveira, "Labview FPGA FOC implementation for synchronous permanent magnet motor speed control," in *2014 11th IEEE/IAS International Conference on Industry Applications*, 2014, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/INDUSCON.2014.7059427.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nam Duong Le received a master's degree in Electronic Engineering from the University of Danang in 2011. Since 2004 he has been a lecturer at the Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Quy Nhon University. Currently, he is a PhD student at the Institute of Engineering and Automation - Hanoi University of Science and Technology. His research interests include electrical machine drive, Power electronics, electric vehicles, FPGA. He can be contacted at email: lenamduong@qnu.edu.vn.

Le Quang Linh is currently a student at Hanoi University of Science and Technology. His major at Hanoi University of Science and Technology is Control Engineering and Automation and will complete his course in 2021. His research interests include power electronics, electric vehicles, electrical machine drive, FPGA. He can be contacted at email: linh.lq174016@sis.hust.edu.vn.

Nguyen Tien Huy Cong is currently a student at Hanoi University of Science and Technology, his major is Control Engineering and Automation., he is studying his engineer degree at Hanoi University of Science and Technology and will complete it in 2022. His research interests include power electronics, electrical machine drive, FPGA. He can be contacted at email: cong.nth173689@sis.hust.edu.vn.

Phuong Vu received his B.S., M.S., and Ph.D. degrees from Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Vietnam, in 2006, 2008, and 2014, respectively, all in Control Engineering and Automation. Since 2006 he has been employed at Hanoi University of Science and Technology, where he is a lecturer and researcher at school of electrical engineering. His research interests include modeling and controlling of power electronics converters for applications such as photovoltaic, wind system, electrical machine drive. He can be contacted at email: phuong.vuhoang@hust.edu.vn.

Tung Lam Nguyen received the B.S degree in Control and Automation Engineering from Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Hanoi, Vietnam, 2005, the M.S degree from Asian Institute of Technology, 2007, and the Ph. D from The University of Western Australia, 2014. He is current working as a lecturer at Department of Industrial Automation, School of Electrical Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology. He is currently appointed as an Associate Professor in Control Engineering and Automation at Hanoi University of Science and Technology. His research interests include motion control, control system and its applications. He can be contacted at email: lam.nguyentung@hust.edu.vn.